

Table 3 continued

Characters	Cross	Direct effect		Indirect effect				Phenotypic correlation value with single-plant yield	
		F ₂	F ₃	Harvest index		Dry matter production		F ₂	F ₃
				F ₂	F ₃	F ₂	F ₃		
Grain no./panicle	ASD1/Co 33	-0.07	-0.01	0.04	0.01	0.28	0.32	0.29	0.32
	ASD1/ADT36	0.06	0.01	0.05	0.06	0.07	0.09	0.17	0.15
	ASD1/IR50	-0.06	0.01	0.08	0.09	0.30	0.13	0.40**	0.21
100-grain weight	ASD1/Co 33	0.08	-0.01	0.02	-0.08	0.11	0.06	0.20	-0.03
	ASD1/ADT36	-0.03	0.03	0.03	0.20	0.06	0.04	0.07	0.27
	ASD1/IR50	-0.01	0.01	0.03	-0.02	-0.02	0.01	0.01	-0.03
	Residual effect	F ₂	F ₃						
	ASD1/Co 33	0.16	0.06						
	ASD1/ADT36	0.12	0.09						
	ASD1/IR50	0.17	0.07						

**Significant at the 1% level. *Significant at 5% level.

Near-isogenic pairs of indica rices with blast (BI) resistance genes

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Rice BI-resistant near-isogenic pairs involving resistant lines with different genes and corresponding susceptible lines facilitate systematic genetic analysis and molecular study of BI re-

sistance. Each pair has a highly uniform genetic background; they presumably differ only in the resistance genes.

We crossed resistant cultivars Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi, Tetep, and IR58 with the susceptible recurrent parent Zhen-shan 97. Plants segregating for resistance to Chinese BI races ZB15 and ZC15 were selected for successive selfing generations to produce resistant and susceptible lines (see figure). Reactions to Chinese BI races ZB15,

Reaction of near-isogenic pairs to 3 Chinese rice BI fungus races. Hangzhou, China.

Isogenic pairs	Resistance donor	Reaction ^a		
		ZB15	ZC15	ZF1
H1 R and H5 R	Ai-jiao-bai-mi-zi	R	R	S
H1 S and H5 S		S	S	S
H2 R and H3 R		R	R	R
H2 S and H3 S		S	S	S
H4 R and H6 R		R	R	R
H4 S and H6 S		S	S	R
H7 R	Tetep	R	R	R
H7 S		S	S	S
H8 R	IR58	R	R	R
H8 S		S	S	R
H9 R		R	R	S
H9 S		S	S	R
H10 R		S	R	R
H10 S		S	S	S

^a R = resistant, S = susceptible.

ZC15, and ZF1 of 10 near-isogenic pairs differed (see table).

Studies on the molecular biology of rice BI resistance are under way using the pairs. □

Procedure for selecting near-isogenic pair H1 R and H1 S. Lines were backcrossed three times then BC₃ plants were selfed 9 times to produce BC₃F₁₀R and S lines. Selection of other pairs was similar. R = resistant, S = susceptible.

Breeding methods

Anther culturability of rice lines bearing cytoplasmic male sterility

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An increase of anther culturability in cytoplasmic male sterile lines relative to male fertile varieties has been reported in wheat and tobacco. We did a similar study in rice.

The wild abortive cytoplasm (WA), which usually promotes microspore abortion at the uninucleate stage, and the Chinsurah Boro II cytoplasm (BT), which usually triggers a late degeneration of the pollen grains between the binucleated and trinucleated stage, were introduced by successive backcrosses into upland rice varieties IRAT313, IRAT103, and IRAT177.

Cytological observations showed apparently identical aspects of the